

THE EFFECT OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE ON ORGANIZATIONAL PROSPERITY (ANALYTICAL RESEARCH: FOR A SAMPLE OF WORKERS IN THE WASIT PROVINCIAL COUNCIL OFFICE)

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Abstract:

In recent years, the service sector in Iraq has witnessed a significant deterioration in the level of administrative and technical services provided. The research aims to identify the quality of work life and its impact on organizational prosperity, the research problem crystallizes in the statement of intellectual controversy, confusion in the concept of quality of work life. The interaction of philosophical relations in naming the variable by some as the quality of work life and knowing the similarity in its dimensions, as a result of the diversity in the desires of individuals and the intense competition and confusion in calling organizational prosperity (superiority, success, excellence) for most researchers. The researcher focused on the interpretation of these variables, the field problem is manifested through the interviews conducted by the researcher with managers and assistants in (Wasit Governorate Office), explain the real problem that the Diwan suffers from, which is the presence of weakness and the increase in financial problems, because of the delay in approving the budget to support decision-making and balance work and personal life in (quality of work life), lack of interest in the dimensions of organizational prosperity represented in supporting intellectual capital of all kinds, providing adequate infrastructure and weakness in organizational agility, to achieve this, the descriptive analytical method was used. A questionnaire was designed and distributed to the research sample consisting of (department managers, divisional officials, employees) of 160 individuals, to test the research hypotheses, the researchers used a number of statistical methods, including: confirmatory factor analysis, simple and multiple linear regression coefficient, as well as descriptive analytical statistical methods, to determine the impact and importance of the research variables in (Al-Diwan), the statistical program (SPSS.v25) and the (AMOS.V26.) program were relied on in determining the results. The research reached a number of results, the most important of which was the presence of a positive and statistically significant effect of the independent research variable (quality of work life) on the dependent variable (organizational prosperity), that is, the administration (Wasit Governorate Office) employs these techniques to provide the best services that contribute to serving the citizen.

Keywords: quality of work life, organizational prosperity.

Introduction

One of the most important elements of production today (the human element) represented by intellectual capital, The economic, social and technological challenges that keep pace with the development taking place in all fields, we find organizations required to adapt their environment according to all elements and components, based on the importance of the quality of work life in achieving organizational prosperity, in continuity with previous knowledge contributions and for the intellectual enrichment of these topics, this research came to confirm the need to keep pace with these developments, in order to achieve high results in the level of performance and service provision. The importance of research lies in the application and improvement of the quality of work life in order to achieve organizational prosperity. In Wasit Governorate Diwan, which is the mirror of the governorate, the hypothesis was prepared for

the two variables (independent and dependent), how to benefit from it in achieving the results that the research aims to achieve. The research was divided into four sections. The first section includes the research methodology, the second topic includes the theoretical side, as for the third topic, it included the practical aspect of the research, finally, the fourth topic includes the conclusions and recommendations reached by the research.

The first topic: Research methodology

First: The research problem:

Most writers and researchers assert that the present time is a completely different time from the past, both in terms of the intellectual skills required for organizations, or in terms of rapid environmental changes characterized by dynamic and social changes, that the world is witnessing today, which in turn affected the ideas that are presented, these changes have caused a great resonance in the nature of administrative and technical issues, as a result, management thought sought to adopt more important and useful topics for organizations, which called the researchers to direct and pay attention to government organizations to enhance (the quality of work life), building employees' self-confidence, sharing and collaborating with each other, to find alternative paths and reach the appropriate goals under a clear message and build a positive vision for the future, on the other hand, the quality of work life may contribute to the development of organizational prosperity through the mobilization of activities, skills and resources, add integration and coordination between them to create new ideas and the ability to invest and discover opportunities, as well as acquiring the information needed by organizations and focusing on the requirements of the work environment in general and workers in particular, by the interviews they conducted with some of Al-Diwan's affiliates, the two researchers identified the real problem, the bureau suffers from is the lack of funding and the delay in approving the budget, that affect the quality of work life and create the appropriate conditions for good performance and lack of interest in intellectual capital of all kinds (human, structural, operational, social, creative), providing adequate infrastructure and weak organizational agility, which impede achieving (organizational prosperity), in addition to the emergency health conditions represented by the Corona pandemic and reducing working hours, which led to a semi-stop in the work of Al-Diwan and a decrease in levels of effective performance.

Through field coexistence, the problem can be identified within the following question:

What is the impact of quality of work life on organizational prosperity in Wasit Health Department?

Second: The objectives of the research:

The research seeks to achieve a set of objectives, the most important of which are the following:-

1. Building a conceptual and theoretical framework and presenting the philosophy of intellectual contents and the similarities and differences in points of view across the research variables.
2. Analyzing and presenting the dimensions of the quality of work life and the dimensions of organizational prosperity, and an attempt to guide the directors of departments, the divisions, and the employees of the Bureau about the nature of the two variables (independent and dependent) and their importance in work.
3. Access to a realistic model of the study by testing the impact hypotheses, which illustrate the interaction between the research variables in proportion to the service reality and improving the quality of work life in order to achieve organizational prosperity in the Bureau in particular and the governorate in general.

Third: The importance of research:

1. The research presents philosophical and intellectual discussions related to the nature of the two variables, namely (quality of work life and organizational prosperity).
2. The research combined the field of human resources in the variable of quality of work life and the field of organizational behavior in the variable of organizational prosperity.
3. The importance of field research shows in choosing the service sector, which is one of the most important sectors in the country as it provides services that highlight the social and human values of citizens.
4. The research came in order to prepare a society free of ignorance and underdevelopment while providing systematic solutions to various problems and to create a good quality of work life that rises towards achieving organizational prosperity through the interpretation and analysis of information for a variety of statistical studies.
5. The research provides a database that can be used in (Wasit Governorate Office) in order to stand in the face of problems, challenges and future changes and to update methods of work practice in a way that enhances the importance of the quality of work life in organizational prosperity.

Fourth: The default search scheme:

Figure (1) prepared by the researcher based on previous literature

Fifth: Research hypotheses

The main research hypothesis: which states (there is no statistically significant effect of the quality of work life on organizational prosperity).

The following sub-hypothesis (comprehensive) is branched from it: which states (there is no statistically significant effect of the dimensions of the quality of work life represented by (social integration, participation in decision-making, work-life balance in organizational prosperity)).

Sixth: The research community and its sample

The target community included all the administrative staff on the permanent staff, which numbered 320 employees; directors of departments, division officials and employees of the Diwan exclusively. The research depended on the selection of a simple random sample and according to the equation (Steven Thompson). The researcher distributed 175 questionnaires directly to the research sample, in 25 sections of the employees of the (Wasit Governorate Office), where 15 questionnaires not valid for analysis were retrieved, the total was 160 questionnaires ready for statistical analysis, i.e. 91 of the total number.

The second topic

The theoretical side of the research

First: the concept of quality of work life

The main objective of improving the quality of work life stems from how to prepare a motivated, motivating, creative and innovative human force that adapts to a good and appropriate work environment with the needs and desires of the parties contributing to determining the type of work (Rasmi et al., 2018: 102) and custom (Al-Mutlaq, 2021: 363) quality of life Work “It is an important indicator for achieving organizational success by

providing a healthy and appropriate environment that helps human resources management in facing future crises and challenges.” The researchers believe that the quality of work life:

It is a dynamic process that aims to invest the efforts of workers and benefit from them in achieving the goals, while providing an appropriate healthy environment so that they can live in luxury at work, giving them participation in decision-making, encouraging cooperation, treating everyone fairly and adopting the principle of democracy at work.

Second: The importance of quality of work life

The importance of the quality of work life is evident through its impact on the activities of the organization and its relations with the external environment, directly and indirectly, and this has been confirmed by analytical and applied studies and research in changing and different environments. Therefore, you see (Al-Dababsa, 2017: 33-37) that any defect in the work environment of the organization affects its success and looking to the distant future. The importance of the quality of work life has been explained in the following:

1. Supporting and developing human relations.
2. Reducing the rate of work turnover away from injustice and resolving conflicts under a good work environment.
3. Developing competencies and increasing effectiveness.
4. The best use of the resources available in the organization.
5. Providing an appropriate work environment in all respects (physical, moral, organizational) and facing competitions and challenges.

The researchers believe: The quality of work life is the basic seed in the success of organizations in order to find a match between the needs and desires of workers on the one hand and the requirements of the organization on the other hand, and to create a cooperative atmosphere under safe and healthy conditions, to achieve the welfare of workers and increase job satisfaction.

Third: Dimensions of quality of work life

The study (Mahmoud, 2020: 1657) confirmed that the dimensions of the quality of work life are the realization of the active role in the commitment of workers and making them more motivated to work and upgrading the efforts of workers in achieving the practices made by the Human Resources Department in mitigating and reducing the problems facing workers and setting a mechanism for developing and maximizing their capabilities and capabilities mental and physical. (Qahiri, 2020:30) believes that the dimensions of work life “are the outcome of the interaction of a group of programs and systems related to improving and developing the human capital aspects of the organization, which are (good job design, implementation of the wages and rewards system, allowing workers to participate in decision-making, Providing occupational health and safety, the prevailing good relations, which is positively reflected on the satisfaction, loyalty and commitment of employees).

The researchers believe that the dimensions of the quality of work life: are determined according to the work environment of each organization. The dimensions of the quality of work life were selected (social integration, participation in decision-making, work-life balance) after identifying the existence of problems in these three dimensions associated with work in Wasit Governorate Office, which is the subject of the research, which will be clarified according to the following paragraphs:

1. Social Integration:

Social integration means overcoming some lapses when they occur with respect and a humane style and with everyone based on the concept of mutual respect and friendliness, and in order for the organization to be a place for mutual cooperation and where security and safety prevail, and for the working individual to feel that he is important in his workplace, social integration must be achieved through the individual's endowment with a healthy organizational culture And its good relationship with the organization's work environment (Assaf & Alhour, 2018:18).

The researchers believe that social integration: It is the process that achieves organizational success in the organization by identifying the information about the work and receiving the job with pride and the individual's feeling that he is an important person in the organization and creating friendly and complementary relationships with other workers and reducing administrative control imposed on workers and making self-censorship in a work environment the organization.

2. Participation in decision-making:

It is the process that achieves a kind of job harmony in the work environment and gives workers the opportunity to express their opinions and ideas and uses modern methods to improve the quality of work and reduce work obstacles in quality and quantity between workers and employers (Al-Manan, 2018: 16).

The researchers believe that the process of participation in decision-making: is the process of interaction and cooperation between employees and employers to develop a work plan, choose alternatives, make final decisions, take and implement them, and reach positive results through the following:

1. Gaining experience and skill by participating in work and exchanging opinions.
2. Allow individuals to participate in putting their new ideas into circulation to make final decisions.
3. Enhancing professional activity and raising the statistical spirit.
4. Reducing the errors committed through individual action.
5. Work within groups and the professional team to reach rational decisions.

3. Balance between work and life:

The concept of work-life balance refers to achieving “stability and integration between work life and personal life, according to the study (Al-Sabbagh and Ashour, 2020: 659), and the confirmation of the United Nations in 2011 in one of its reports and at its sixty-sixth session that work-life balance is one of the components Strategies of human resource management and positively affects the individual’s work and organizational and emotional commitment. Therefore, when the individual is psychologically and emotionally stable and does not suffer from any family problems, that is, there is compatibility between work and personal life, which is felt by the lack of stress and psychological burden. The fairness in treatment and the appropriate passage of efforts Individuals feel happy while maintaining personal dignity, self-confidence, and other social considerations such as status and reputation, in addition to a sense of loyalty to leadership, commitment and job satisfaction.” (Hussain, 2021: 201).

The researchers believe that the balance between work and life: It is the success that organizations achieve in their working life, and it is the starting point towards bright horizons, which is reflected in a positive and fruitful return. Low turnover and workers' sense of organized love, belonging and loyalty.

Second: Organizational Prosperity

First: The Concept of Organizational Prosperity:

The word (prosperity) means continuous development and improvement in order to satisfy the needs of the worker in the community, while the word (organizational) means the achievement of the goals set in each organization within a community entity with specific features, and achieving the goals of the organization means the existence of an effective social entity, with clearly defined boundaries. Which seeks to achieve specific goals and objectives (Hafez et al., 2019: 212) The continuation of the success of organizations is no longer an easy matter, and it needs high and effective performance, consistent with the rapid environmental changes taking place in business organizations (Chew, 2005:87), and from another angle (Al-Shibani, 2014: 67) referred to the concept of organizational prosperity by the Turkish Language Association, which prepared a dictionary about this concept, which means a better life and prosperity, living comfort and acquiring wealth with better conditions, or it is the achievement of the achievements and results of a cohesive and synergistic work team and common goals among workers and management. As for the opinion of the two researchers (Abdullah and Saleh, 2022: 225), they mentioned the concept of organizational prosperity as the stage that the organization reaches success and provides security, stability, survival and long-term sustainability through its creativity, competitive advantage, organizational agility and speed of response in the face of challenges and competitors. Providing the required services and products.

The researchers believe that organizational prosperity: It is a common goal that all organizations seek to achieve and find levels of stability, adaptation, environmental alignment, and achieve full creativity and future success in the long term.

Second: The Importance of Organizational Prosperity:

Organizations are generally concerned with the issue of organizational prosperity in order to provide products and services that satisfy the customer and satisfy his requirements. (Mohammed, 2020: 272) indicated that the importance of organizational prosperity lies in the following:-

1. The comprehensive and distinguished organizations that carry the index of success and creativity are the ones that recognize all the requirements of the turbulent competitive environment and how to develop possible alternatives under unexpected circumstances.
2. What increases the level of success, growth, organizational excellence and prosperity of organizations is the achievement of sustainable profits.
3. The importance of prosperity enhances and contributes to the achievement of intellectual and material capital.
4. The importance of prosperity is evident in developing human capabilities, gaining customer satisfaction and creating sustainable competitive value by providing other products and services.

In the same context, it was the opinion of (Hamid and others, 2021: 316) that the importance of organizational prosperity can be clarified as follows:

1. The organizational prosperity goes beyond the current situation in the selection of qualified human elements and those with the necessary capabilities.
2. It gives employees a suitable environment for growth and development and promote development in business organizations.
3. The feeling of working people in life and vitality and looking forward to everything that is new and creative.
4. Positive reflection on the lives of employees through increasing organizational sustainability.

The researchers believe that the importance of organizational prosperity is represented in the following: With great interest because it expresses the partnership between activity and learning, and through it workers feel vitality and race to acquire science and knowledge and raise the level of job performance, which is a positive factor that seeks to motivate the individual to work tasks and show confidence in achieving the set goals. The researcher summarized the importance in a number of points as follows:

1. Organizational prosperity helps in activating the strategic and administrative decisions in the organization.
2. Strengthening the infrastructure of business organizations.
3. Develop employees and increase the growth of the organization and pay attention to creativity and intellectual capital.

Third: Dimensions of Organizational Prosperity:

Due to the lack of studies and research that dealt directly with the issue of organizational prosperity, as well as the scarcity and relatively newness of the subject in relation to the Iraqi environment in general. Wasit Governorate in particular (according to the researchers' knowledge) and despite the presence of similar topics such as (organizational excellence, organizational success), which are very close to the concept of organizational prosperity, the researchers found that there is a study that coincided with two dimensions of its dimensions, namely (intellectual capital, agility Organizational) with the environment and place of application in the office of Wasit Governorate, which is a study (Niammuad, et. al, 2014:197) and because of the different opinions of researchers from one researcher to another, researchers and writers differed in describing the dimensions of organizational prosperity and according to the point of view of each researcher and writer, and according to the study (Omair 139, 2019: The success of the organization comes from an approach if the organization has (competitive advantage, strategic agility, creativity, intellectual capital) at that time we say that the organization is distinguished in organizational prosperity. The researchers were able to identify some dimensions through which you can find interpretation and analysis of information and data to find solutions to the problems of the department under study in Wasit Governorate Diwan and to give a clear picture and according to the researchers' vision, with the availability of scientific (Arabic and foreign) references in addition to university theses and theses, as well as Networks (Internet) and after identifying the existence of problems in these three dimensions (intellectual capital, organizational agility, infrastructure) associated with working in (Wasit Governorate Diwan), a study was approved (Al-Rubaie, 2021: 159) that the dimensions of organizational prosperity are (Creativity, Infrastructure, Intellectual Capital) which are compatible with the infrastructure dimension in question, which will be clarified according to the following paragraphs:

1. Intellectual Capital:

"Intellectual capital is all the knowledge resources owned by the organization, which are characterized by dynamism and innovation, and which work to ensure its progress and achieve competitive advantage in the light of knowledge markets." According to that vision, it was stated (Sadq et al., 2020: 2642) "The success of the organization depends on the management's ability to provide an appropriate environment and obtain experiences, knowledge and ideas from intellectual capital, which is the best asset of the organization in investment and profit making. In the same context, the opinion was" Yusef, 2021: 882" that intellectual capital is the intellectual and mental capabilities and competencies possessed by workers in organizations to achieve sustainable market value and raise levels of growth and constructive core resources in light of the sudden challenges of senior management in business organizations. (Omer et al., 2021: 91) indicated that it is a process that aims to achieve a market value greater than the book value of a group of capital (human, physical, structural).

The researchers believe that intellectual capital: It is the enhancement of human capabilities and capabilities, and it represents one of the organization's treasures and its hidden weapon.

2. Organizational agility:

The first appearance of the concept of organizational agility in a factory in the United States of America was in the late eighties and early nineties of the last century, due to the emergence of globalization and the increase and expansion in economic and social fields. Business organizations through detection, sensing, inquiry and comprehensive forecasting of organizational areas (Al-Shaibani, 2014: 154) The study (Mohammed, 2020: 27) confirmed that organizational agility is one of the sources of availability of economic resources and the organization's willingness to continuous vigilance through its learning and knowledge base, and that agility Regulatory organizations are emerging in the globalization economy, and this is reflected positively on their capabilities in continuous improvement, growth, profit and sustainability. Quoting (Omar, 2020: 53), he indicated, There are main elements of organizational agility (sherehiy, 2008: 9-10) that can be clarified as follows:

- 1) Speed and flexibility.
- 2) Exploitation of technological capabilities.
- 3) Customized high quality products.
- 4) Response to rapid changes.
- 5) Diligent work with external environment variables.
- 6) Organizational cooperation at work.
- 7) Exploiting opportunities and providing alternatives.
- 8) Value-added content and high information for products and services.
- 9) Achieving (the reactive aspect) of the ability in organizational adaptation and (the proactive aspect) of the ability in organizational flexibility.

The two researchers consider organizational agility: it is the organization's ability to achieve organizational prosperity through the organization's flexibility in the face of rapid changes taking place in business organizations and unexpected circumstances and the extent of the organization's response to these circumstances. Growth, profit and sustainability.

3. Infrastructure:

It is one of the most important elements or components that develop the pace of the global economy and is an important measure for judging the state or organization and the main driver of economic activities, and because it helps to provide the goods and services necessary and necessary for the sustainability of life, such as building villages and neighborhoods, electric power generators, sewage networks, tunnels and building bridges. Social capital for the development of industry and is directly linked to industrial wealth (Sultani and Benzawi, 2015: 76). As for the opinion of (Rasheed and Karima, 2018: 14), they refer to it as "a set of interconnected physical components of systems and processes in the manufacture and provision of goods and services necessary and necessary to achieve sustainability and provide The conditions of community life and the addition of basic services such as building schools and hospitals." (Al-Omari, 2020: 107) indicated that infrastructure "is the basic pillar in business and management organizations and is the cornerstone on which all their operations and management are based, and the extent to which they achieve the set goals, and it consists of

five elements A basic need for every organization looking for creativity in its work and continued success. These elements are: (organizational culture, financial environment, etc.). Diya, organizational structure, information technology, and physical knowledge and sees (Al-Rubaie, 163): "The infrastructure is a set of interconnected structural elements that provide a framework that supports the overall structure of development in the organization, in a way that facilitates the provision of basic services and improve the productivity of the organization for long-term success.

The researchers believe that the infrastructure: It is the basis for every organization that aims to produce goods and services, provide and develop needs, satisfy all working parties and develop vital facilities in all local and organizational fields combined to achieve the goals of organizations, growth and development and keep pace with technological technologies.

The third topic

The Practical Aspect of Research

Test the main hypothesis that states: (There is no statistically significant effect on the quality of work life and organizational prosperity):

The test model was formulated for the purpose of verifying the validity of the main research hypotheses related to the nature of the impact and on this basis the hypothesis can be tested and the standard estimates clarified on the impact of the (independent) variable, the quality of work life on the dependent variable (organizational prosperity) and as in Figure (2).

Figure (2) Normative estimates of the impact of quality of work life on organizational prosperity

Figure (2) shows the standard estimates of the simple regression model, as the quality of work life variable (x) represents the independent variable, while the organizational prosperity variable (Y) represents the dependent variable, and we note that the standard estimated value amounted to (Beta = 0.78), meaning that the quality of work life has an impact And a significant contribution to organizational prosperity. He also explained the value of (R²), which amounted to (0.61), and this ratio explains 61% of the dependent variable (organizational prosperity) by the influence of the independent variable (quality of work life), while the other 39% are due to other external factors and reasons in addition to The effect coefficient between the variables was (0.778), and this value indicates the presence of a direct effect between the variables. Non-normative estimates of the impact of quality of work life on organizational prosperity can be illustrated as shown in Figure (3).

Figure (3) Nonparametric estimates of the impact of quality of work life on organizational prosperity

Figure (3) shows the nonparametric estimates of the simple linear regression model, as (0.80) represents the value of the marginal slope, and the value of the fixed term was (0.42) and the value of the error was (0.18), and this is evidence of the morality of the model, and therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative, which states (there is an effect with Statistical significance of the quality of work life in organizational prosperity) and the regression equation can be as follows: - work life quality (0.80) + 0.42 = organizational prosperity as in Table (1)

Table (1) estimations of the impact model for the quality of work life variable in the organizational prosperity variable

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Organizational prosperity	<---	quality of work life	0.805	0.052	15.614	***

1. Overall Sub-Hypothesis Test:

The test model was formulated for the purpose of verifying the validity of the research hypothesis related to the nature of the effect according to the comprehensive sub-hypothesis, which states (there is no statistically significant effect relationship to remove the quality of work life and organizational prosperity). (Social integration, participation in decision-making, work-life balance) in the dependent variable (organizational prosperity) as shown in Figure (4).

Figure (4) Standard estimates of the impact of quality of work life dimensions on organizational prosperity

Figure (4) shows the standard estimates of the multiple regression model, as the dimensions (X_23,X_22,X_21) represent the independent variable, the quality of work life in (social

integration, participation in decision-making, work-life balance), while the organizational prosperity variable (Y) represents the variable We note that the standard estimated value amounted to (Beta=0.23,0.35,0.34), meaning that the dimensions of the quality of work life have a significant impact and contribution to organizational prosperity. He explained the value of (R²), which amounted to (0.61) and this ratio explains 61% of the dependent variable (Organizational prosperity) due to the influence of independent variables (social integration, participation in decision-making, work-life balance), while the other 39% are due to other external factors and causes, in addition to the coefficient of influence between the variables indicating a direct effect. Non-normative estimates of the impact of quality of work life on organizational prosperity can be illustrated as shown in Figure (5).

Figure (5) Nonparametric estimates the impact of the dimensions of quality of work life on organizational prosperity

Figure (5) shows the nonparametric estimates of the multiple linear regression model, as (0.21,0.29,0.30) represents the value of the marginal slope for each of the dimensions, and the error value is (0.18), and this is evidence of the significance of the model, and therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative, which states (there is an effect It is statistically significant to remove the quality of work life in organizational prosperity) and thus the equation of the simple linear regression is as follows:-

Organizational prosperity = 0.30 social integration + 0.29 participation in decision-making + 0.21 work-life balance.

Table (2) shows the impact model estimates for the dimensions of the quality of work life, which represent (social integration, work-life participation, balancing in decision-making) in the dependent variable (organizational prosperity).

Table (2) the impact model estimates for the dimensions of the quality of work life in the organizational prosperity variable

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Organizational prosperity	<---	Social integration	0.205	0.061	3.377	***
Organizational prosperity	<---	Participation in making decisions	0.303	0.055	5.508	***
Organizational prosperity	<---	Balance work and life	0.295	0.056	5.280	***

The fourth topic

Conclusions and recommendations

First: the conclusions

1. There is a significant effect of the independent variable (quality of work life) with its dimensions (social integration, participation in decision-making, work-life balance) on the dependent variable (organizational prosperity), where the sample answers were oriented towards agreement at a high level and the existence of an error value for each dimension. With a percentage of (0.18) an indication that the quality of work life has an effective impact and contribution to (the Bureau) of organizational prosperity, and it became clear through the interview conducted by the researcher, where the managers in the research sample indicated that there is a low degree in the dimension (social integration) that prevails among the employees of the Bureau. Which could affect their performance to complete their jobs in the required manner as well as its direct impact on their creativity and innovations, which prompted the researcher to pay attention to this dimension and put it at the forefront of these dimensions in order to develop the correct and feasible mechanisms for success and to activate organizational prosperity and to allow workers to explode their energies. And creative talents may lead the organization to success and excellence.
2. The results of the quality of work life indicated a weakness in the dimension (work-life balance) and indicate that (Wasit Governorate Office) is concerned, to an acceptable degree, in securing a good working environment for workers.
3. The research found that most of the managers and officials in (Wasit Governorate Diwan) have good insight in studying environmental variables as a result of previous experience and deep understanding they have, and they are of a high level to deal with emergency events that require intuitiveness and speed in making the appropriate decision, but it remains an investment and activation. The role of these experiences and capabilities is at a weak level in critical and necessary situations.

Second: Recommendations

1. The necessity of paying more attention to the quality of work life in the dimension (social integration) and urging all workers to cooperate and teamwork with each other and their personal conviction and belief that the positive work they do will benefit them in particular, and the Bureau in general. And activating the social media channels of employees, through the creation of teamwork teams or groups.
2. The Bureau needs to pay attention to the dimension of (work-life balance) and to achieve compatibility between the working life and the private life of the employees. Which allows to achieve high levels of creativity among workers, which called the researcher to pay attention to this dimension within the dimensions of the quality of work life in order to achieve the welfare of workers.

3. Creating a special section or division to manage the creators and distinguished people in (Wasit Governorate Diwan) in order to achieve high performance and contain their new ideas and support them financially and morally. This is considered an intellectual contribution to persuading the workers that their work will return to them with a positive return.

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